

RhizomeBridge: real-time communication between native audio plugins and Node.js via shared memory

Lorenzo Ballerini

Giuseppe Verdi Conservatory of Music
Como, Italy

lorenzo.ballerini@conservatoriocomo.it

Valerio Orlandini

Luigi Cherubini Conservatory of Music
Florence, Italy

valerio.orlandini@stud-phd.consfi.it

ABSTRACT

RhizomeBridge is a VST/AU plugin that enables real-time, bidirectional communication with minimal latency and sample-accurate precision between a Digital Audio Workstation (DAW) and an external Node.js process. Unlike protocol-based approaches that add overhead through serialisation, polling, or network delays, it establishes a direct connection between the native audio callback and the JavaScript environment via shared memory and semaphores.

Audio and MIDI are exchanged in raw binary format through native Node.js add-ons. A custom data organisation ensures temporal alignment and integrity even in asynchronous contexts.

Once in the JavaScript environment, data can be processed, routed back to the DAW, or forwarded to web applications, IoT devices, and collaborative platforms via protocols such as WebRTC or WebSocket. This upper layer is decoupled from the critical DAW \leftrightarrow Node.js link, which remains deterministic and sample-accurate.

The system has been tested in scenarios including bidirectional local communication, real-time audio/MIDI processing in Node.js and browsers, and audiovisual performances on mobile and web platforms. Results are presented alongside a technical overview of the architecture and latency evaluation.

By bridging low-level audio infrastructure with high-level JavaScript environments, RhizomeBridge provides a modular and reusable architecture that connects web ecosystems with professional DAWs, supporting distributed collaboration and enabling hybrid practices in composition, interaction, and creative coding.

1. INTRODUCTION

The continuous development of Web Audio API, AudioWorklet [19], WebAssembly [20], and communication protocols such as WebRTC [18] and WebSocket [22] has significantly expanded the browser's potential as a platform for real-time multimedia. These technologies have made the web a suitable environment for audiovisual synthesis, capable of handling complex signal chains with high temporal

resolution, approaching DAW standards.

At the same time, a wide range of external environments have emerged, from Node.js runtime [15] to embedded devices and distributed systems, offering complementary functionality for data processing and control. Node.js, in particular, can act as a bridge between server-side processes and web-based multimedia environments, enabling integration across heterogeneous domains.

With the convergence of web and native technologies, establishing a stable, bidirectional, low-latency dialogue between DAWs and JavaScript-based environments has become increasingly crucial.

Existing technologies including Open Sound Control (OSC)¹, WebSocket, or virtual loopback devices such as JACK² and BlackHole³ offer flexibility, yet they add protocol layers or external components that increase complexity without guaranteeing sample-accurate synchronisation between audio and MIDI streams, as expected in native plugin architectures.

These limitations have motivated the design of RhizomeBridge (see Figure 1), a native, modular plugin that establishes a precise, synchronised two-way communication layer between the DAW and a Node.js environment, and by extension with web-based applications.

Audio and control data are exchanged for real-time processing, while preserving temporal consistency and sample accuracy. Communication takes place via shared memory (SHM) segments, accessible both from a JUCE-based audio plugin [8] and from Node.js through native C++ add-ons compiled as `.node` modules. Each SHM structure is associated with a semaphore, ensuring safe and consistent access.

This design avoids the overhead of process communication protocols such as serialisation, data conversion, or active polling, enabling real-time data transfers with minimal latency. SHM is widely supported in Unix-like systems (macOS, Linux), with equivalent mechanisms available on Windows⁴.

The system supports both unidirectional and bidirectional modes of operation, including dynamic SHM naming, multiple instances, and parallel streams. In addition, plugin systems allow declaring an expected processing latency, which the host can use for automatic alignment.

This architecture integrates external processes into a syn-

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¹<https://opensoundcontrol.stanford.edu>

²<https://jackaudio.org>

³<https://existential.audio/blackhole/>

⁴<https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/windows/win32/memory/creating-named-shared-memory>

chronous, interoperable framework. As a reusable infrastructure, RhizomeBridge extends DAW workflows to web-based performance systems, IoT interfaces, hybrid installations, real-time audiovisual works, and collaborative or distributed environments. This allows artists, developers, and researchers to design new interactive scenarios without altering the underlying DAW engine.

Figure 1: RhizomeBridge GUI.

2. CONTEXT AND COMPARATIVE FRAMEWORK

Integrating DAWs with external web environments is a recurring goal in projects exploring sound, interaction, and distributed computing. Many solutions address this challenge with architectures oriented to specific purposes, such as remote synchronisation, audiovisual streaming, or distributed control, typically tied to the application context.

RhizomeBridge operates at a more general architectural level, avoiding network protocols or middleware, and providing a deterministic and reusable infrastructure. Any latency introduced by transport protocols or architectural extensions, such as browsers, IoT devices, or remote transmissions, is unavoidable, but remains aligned with the DAW’s native audio domain thanks to a stable and consistent base.

The following subsections provide an overview of approaches to integrating audio systems with external environments, ranging from native and plugin-based architectures to browser-centric models. While some of these solutions aim at direct interaction with DAWs, others focus on real-time exchanges between networked or hybrid platforms. These systems are referenced for comparison with the principles that guide RhizomeBridge: deterministic data access, independence from transport protocols, and separation between critical audio processing and asynchronous communication.

2.1 Transport and Application Protocols: UDP, TCP, WebSocket, OSC

Approaches to integrating audio environments and external processes often rely on transport protocols (UDP, TCP) and application layers such as WebSocket or OSC.

UDP, with its low-latency connectionless nature, is widely used for transmitting audio or MIDI in real-time systems (e.g. LOLA [6], Fast-Music [2]). OSC, typically built on

UDP, is popular in artistic and academic contexts for structured data exchange, with extensions such as Audio Over OSC (AOO)⁵ supporting audio transmission.

TCP is unsuitable for real-time audio because its reliability mechanisms introduce jitter and buffering. WebSocket, which relies on it, is often used in browser-based musical systems for transmitting control information, where guaranteed delivery is more important than timing accuracy, as in the work of Vinay and Boulanger [17]. This makes it adequate for control data but unsuitable for continuous audio/MIDI streams that demand stable low-latency performance.

Although these protocols enable flexible communication, they add unnecessary overhead, particularly when running on the same machine. In such cases, direct interaction without transport layers offers a more efficient solution, reducing latency and preserving bandwidth for distributed scenarios such as browsers, IoT devices, or collaborative environments.

2.2 DAW plugins with network support

Several projects extend audio plugins (VST, AU) to transmit signals over a network, typically for remote collaboration between DAW instances. Systems such as Waves Stream⁶ implement efficient audio/video transport between geographically separated studios.

These solutions, however, target synchronisation between homogeneous DAW environments rather than exposing audio data to external processes or programming environments such as Node.js or browsers.

2.3 Browser-centric environments and JavaScript frameworks

Frameworks such as WAAX [3], Web Audio Modules (WAM) [10], and proposals for a standardized Web Audio plugin architecture [1] have extended the Web Audio API to turn the browser into a modular, controllable environment in real time. Complementary tools such as Csound for Web [23], FAUST [12], and RNBO [5] further support the design of portable audio engines that can be deployed across a wide range of targets including desktop, mobile, embedded systems, and the web. Together, these frameworks enable the development of synthesis engines, DSP modules, and interactive interfaces, leveraging client-side audio pipelines, and ensuring compatibility with external devices.

Such environments typically operate in isolation from the DAW’s native audio engine and, when integration is needed, communication is often mediated through operating system-level routing solutions such as Jack or BlackHole. While research and open frameworks have explored network-based or protocol-level extensions (e.g. WebMIDI, OSC, WebSocket, WebRTC), a tight, sample-accurate integration with DAW plugin architectures remains an open area of investigation.

2.4 WebRTC for Real-Time Audio Streaming

Projects such as JackTrip-WebRTC [16] demonstrate the possibility of using WebRTC as an infrastructure for low-latency audio streaming between remote nodes, as in distributed music collaboration contexts. These systems offer an effective solution for A/V exchange over public networks, thanks to integrated support in modern browsers and com-

⁵<https://aoo.iem.sh>

⁶<https://www.waves.com/plugins/waves-stream>

patibility with peer-to-peer protocols.

Generally, such architectures operate outside the DAW ecosystem, although it is possible to implement plugins that directly integrate WebRTC or WebSocket to communicate with JavaScript environments or browsers. In this case, the transport and processing logic tend to merge, binding the plugin to a specific destination or configuration. Such frameworks are highly integrated and effective within specific workflows, but less suitable for contexts where interoperability, dynamic routing, or remote orchestration are required.

2.5 Positioning RhizomeBridge in the Architecture Landscape

RhizomeBridge is not an alternative to protocols such as OSC, WebSocket, or WebRTC, nor to frameworks like Web Audio Modules. Instead, it operates upstream, offering the DAW a stable, deterministic interface for interacting with these tools.

It provides native infrastructure that preserves temporal consistency between audio and MIDI through frame identifiers and structured metadata. Data is exposed in the JavaScript environment as binary buffers, ready to be processed, routed, or transformed.

By using shared memory, RhizomeBridge avoids protocol encapsulation: information is transmitted in native form, exactly as produced by the DAW. Once accessible in JavaScript, it can be integrated with external protocols or processing frameworks, while maintaining architectural separation between the DAW’s audio domain and higher-level transport or computation layers.

The goal is to provide synchronous, reusable access to binary data through an interoperable infrastructure that supports both technical integration and artistic applications, while leaving protocol choice and stream handling to the system designer

3. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

3.1 Communication via Shared Memory and Semaphores

The architecture (see Figure 2) is modular and extensible. The inter-process communication (IPC) between the plugin and the external Node.js process is based on shared memory regions (SHM) and POSIX semaphores [9]. Four independent shared memory blocks are used in total: two dedicated to audio, one for output from the DAW (input to Node.js), one for input to the DAW (output from Node.js), and two for MIDI data, following the same directional logic.

Each memory segment is matched to a dedicated POSIX semaphore, resulting in four independent synchronisation channels. These standard mechanisms minimise data copying between processes, avoid serialisation, and ensure block-synchronous, low-latency communication suitable for real-time audio.

Synchronisation follows a deterministic signalling model: when a process writes a block, it sets a readiness flag (`readyFlag`) and signals the semaphore. The reader process then waits on the semaphore (via `sem_wait()`), reads the data upon activation, and clears the `readyFlag`, restoring the memory segment to a neutral state for the next cycle.

This approach is blocking-oriented. Although schemes

Figure 2: System architecture diagram: the JUCE plugin communicates with Node.js via SHM, which in turn interacts with external environments.

such as single-producer single-consumer (SPSC) ring buffers are often preferred in real-time audio to prevent wait states, here a semaphore mechanism was chosen to minimise absolute latency: as soon as a block is written, the reader is awakened immediately, avoiding the fixed minimum delay inherent in lock-free designs. Since in the next stage a ring buffer might be required to handle jitter and clock drift between Node.js and external applications (e.g., the browser), adding another at this point would only increase latency. Using SHMs with semaphores at this stage therefore maximises responsiveness and ensures sample-accurate synchronisation between the plugin and the host process, effectively treating Node.js as an integral part of the plugin despite being an external entity.

3.1.1 Shared Memory Structure – Audio Buffer

The audio shared memory buffer is implemented as a fixed-size `Float32Array` (2054 values). This structure allows consistent, low-latency communication between the plugin (e.g., VST/AU) and the Node.js environment, and is designed to be compatible with Web Audio technologies such as `AudioWorklet`.

As shown in Table 1, the buffer layout includes both metadata and interleaved PCM audio samples:

Table 1: Shared audio buffer structure

Index	Field	Type
0	<code>frameId</code>	<code>float32</code>
1	<code>numChannels</code>	<code>float32</code>
2	<code>sampleRate</code>	<code>float32</code>
3	<code>blockSize</code>	<code>float32</code>
4	<code>reserved1</code>	<code>float32</code>
5	<code>reserved2</code>	<code>float32</code>
6–2053	<code>audioData[2048]</code>	<code>float32</code>

- `frameId` is a circular counter (0–255) incremented at each audio processing block. It provides synchronisation with the MIDI shared buffer and enables loss detection. If a frame is missing, silence can be introduced to maintain temporal continuity.
- `numChannels` and `sampleRate` define the current stream configuration. These values may be read in JavaScript to configure the `AudioContext` or inform

audio graph logic (e.g., dynamic buffer allocation or resampling).

- **blockSize** indicates the number of valid samples in the current frame. Even though the shared buffer is statically sized (2048 samples), the effective length depends on the host DAW buffer size. This allows flexibility and avoids over-processing on the JS side.
- **reserved1** and **reserved2** are padding fields, reserved for future use (e.g., status flags, timestamps, or compatibility markers), allowing extensions without breaking the memory layout.
- **audioData[2048]** contains interleaved float32 PCM samples. For stereo streams, the format is [L0, R0, L1, R1, ...], directly compatible with Web Audio graphs. This interleaved layout was intentionally chosen over JUCE’s non-interleaved convention to enable seamless integration with AudioWorklet-based processing.

3.1.2 Shared Memory Structure – MIDI Buffer

A dedicated shared memory buffer is allocated with a fixed size of 512 bytes. Both incoming and outgoing MIDI data (DAW ↔ JS) follow the same compact binary layout, enabling bidirectional low-latency control with sample-accurate timing.

The buffer is structured as a flat `Uint8Array`, organized into 7-byte blocks. As summarized in Table 2, the first 7 bytes encode the *header*:

Table 2: MIDI shared memory header structure

Index	Field	Type
0	frameId	uint8
1	fader1	uint8
2	fader2	uint8
3	fader3	uint8
4	fader4	uint8
5	numMessages	uint8
6	reserved	uint8

- **frameId** (byte 0): a circular block index (0–255), synchronized with the audio shared buffer to ensure temporal alignment. Any mismatch allows detection of dropped or late blocks, preventing desynchronisation.
- **Fader1–4** (bytes 1–4): four 8-bit values mapped to virtual faders in the plugin UI (see Figure 1). These can be used freely (e.g., automation, modulation), allowing the DAW to control external processes or devices.
- **numMessages** (byte 5): number of MIDI events in the current block. This informs the receiver how many 7-byte messages to parse, optimizing performance and avoiding unnecessary reads.
- **reserved** (byte 6): reserved for future extensions.

All subsequent 7-byte segments represent individual MIDI messages (see Table 3); the fields are:

- **frameId** (byte 0): repeated block index, mirroring the MIDI header to support consistency checks.

- **sampleIndex** (bytes 1–2): a 16-bit offset (MSB, LSB) representing the exact sample index where the event should be triggered. This enables sample-accurate scheduling within the current audio block.
- **midiType** (byte 3): event type (1 = Note, 2 = Control Change, 3 = Program Change).
- **channel** (byte 4): MIDI channel (0–15).
- **data1** (byte 5): note number, CC number or program number, according to the event type.
- **data2** (byte 6): velocity, CC value, or unused, according to the event type.

This format is used symmetrically for both incoming and outgoing MIDI buffers, maintaining consistency and simplifying parsing logic on both ends. The sample index is encoded using two 8-bit fields, allowing a 16-bit resolution for placing events within a buffer. This enables sample-accurate alignment, suitable for integration with scheduling mechanisms like `AudioWorklet` or other real-time audio engines.

Table 3: MIDI message block structure

Index	Field	Type
0	frameId	uint8
1	sampleIndex MSB	uint8
2	sampleIndex LSB	uint8
3	midiType	uint8
4	channel	uint8
5	data1	uint8
6	data2	uint8

4. IMPLEMENTATION

4.1 JUCE-Based Plugin Architecture

All shared memory segments used by the system (audio and MIDI, in both directions) are initialised inside the plugin at load time, using the POSIX `shm_open()` function (Listing 1), and persist for the plugin’s lifetime. This ensures that shared buffers are created in the same real-time context as the audio thread, maintaining consistency and priority between writing, synchronisation and the DAW cycle.

```

1 const int numSamples = std::min(buffer.
   getNumSamples(), AUDIO_BUFFER_SIZE);
2 memcpy(audioBuffer->audioData, buffer.
   getReadPointer(0), sizeof(float) *
   numSamples);
3 audioBuffer->readyFlag = 1;
4
5 sem_t* sem = sem_open("/my_semaphore", 0);
6 if (sem != SEM_FAILED)
7 {
8     sem_post(sem);
9     sem_close(sem);
10 }

```

Listing 1: Code snippet from the JUCE plugin, sending the audio block to the shared audio buffer

Within the `processBlock` method, the plugin receives each audio and MIDI block in real time from the DAW.

The audio samples are copied into the outgoing SHM segment (DAW → Node.js), along with a `frameId`, the current `blockSize`, the number of channels and the encoded `sampleRate`. Once the data has been written, the plugin sets a `readyFlag` and posts the associated semaphore to signal the availability of the new block. At the same time, the plugin checks a second, independent SHM segment for incoming audio (Node.js → DAW), and if its flag is set, it reads the samples and copies them to the input buffer (i.e., the buffer returned to the DAW as the plugin’s output). MIDI data is handled in the same way with respective metadata and payload. The process is synchronous with the DAW cycle, respecting the buffer alignment imposed by the host.

4.2 Native Node.js Addons: Access to SHM and Semaphores

To enable real-time communication with shared memory areas instantiated by the JUCE plugin, four native add-ons have been developed for Node.js: two dedicated to audio (input and output) and two for MIDI (input and output). Each add-on can be enabled or disabled depending on the desired configuration. This modular approach allows for the construction of flexible architectures that can include only the streams that are actually necessary for the operating environment (e.g., only audio output for web streaming, or MIDI in/out without audio, etc.).

The add-ons are written in C++, use the N-API (`napi.h`) [14] interface to integrate with the JavaScript runtime, and are compiled with `cmake-js` [4]. This setup facilitates deployment on Unix-like systems, with cross-platform builds possible depending on the underlying system calls used.

Each native module accesses a dedicated shared memory region and its associated semaphore, ensuring isolated and predictable communication. During read and write operations, a shared `readyFlag` is used to ensure mutual exclusion and avoid race conditions across processes. The typical cycle proceeds as follows: the add-on waits for the semaphore using `sem_wait()`, checks that `readyFlag` is set to 1, copies the data into a JavaScript buffer (typically a `Float32Array` for audio or `Uint8Array` for MIDI), then resets the flag to 0. A minimal C++ snippet illustrating this process is shown in Listing 2.

```

1 sem_wait(sem);
2 int shm_fd = shm_open("/shm_audio", O_RDWR,
3   0666);
4 auto* buffer = (SharedAudioBuffer*) mmap(...);
5 if (buffer->readyFlag == 1) {
6   tsfn.BlockingCall(buffer, [...]);
7   buffer->readyFlag = 0;
8 }

```

Listing 2: Minimal C++ cycle in Node.js add-on

A similar mechanism is implemented for writing from Node.js to the plugin, enabling audio or MIDI data to be sent in sync with the DAW’s buffer processing.

Each add-on exposes a dedicated interface to Node.js through native bindings. Once compiled into a `.node` module, it can be imported into the JavaScript environment via a standard `require()` call (Listing 3). The core function `waitForSemaphore` then creates a thread-safe callback from JavaScript and launches a detached thread that monitors a specific semaphore and shared memory.

```

1 const audioAddon = require("./myModules/
2   inAudioBuffer.node");
3 audioAddon.waitForSemaphore("/my_shared_audio",
4   "/my_semaphore", callback);

```

Listing 3: Using the add-on in JavaScript

A schematic representation of the communication flow, from JavaScript activation to shared memory exchange, is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Simplified architecture of the add-on

Add-ons are designed to be autonomous and reusable. Internally they rely on a blocking design using POSIX signalling primitives, while exposing an asynchronous, event-driven API to JavaScript. They can be instantiated in multiple contexts or on separate threads without interfering with one another. The names of shared memory regions and semaphores are passed dynamically at initialisation, allowing multiple instances of RhizomeBridge to run in parallel, on different DAW tracks or for the logical separation of audio and MIDI streams.

Each module is solely responsible for low-level access to memory and operating system resources, while data processing and routing are entirely delegated to higher-level layers. This design enables seamless integration with JavaScript-based environments, making the data readily available for use in web interfaces, multimedia frameworks, or distributed real-time systems.

5. LATENCY AND SYNCHRONISATION

In interactive music systems, latency and jitter are often considered critical obstacles to expressiveness. The literature shows that acceptable latency is contextual rather than absolute [11, 13]. While delays between 20 and 30 ms are generally tolerated in musical applications, the main concern is temporal variability, or jitter, which can compromise timing accuracy and expressiveness. However, their impact depends on context, usage patterns, and user expectations. RhizomeBridge addresses this issue by providing a deterministic communication architecture between plugins and Node.js, ensuring that latency and jitter remain minimal and constant, rather than attempting to eliminate them entirely.

All audio plugins introduce a certain amount of latency, resulting from processing, buffering or I/O management. If not declared to the DAW, this can cause synchronisation

issues [21]. Modern DAWs provide automatic latency compensation when the plugin declares its offset, for example through the `setLatencySamples()` function in JUCE. This allows the host to realign the audio graph and maintain consistency between processed and unprocessed tracks.

In RhizomeBridge, this mechanism is effective thanks to its deterministic internal structure, which avoids network protocols or asynchronous threading. This enables accurate estimation of base latency and reduction of jitter, supporting compensation for further processing stages.

In extended scenarios where RhizomeBridge is combined with non-deterministic pipelines (e.g., WebSocket, OSC, or WebRTC), ring buffers can mitigate jitter, compensate for clock skew, and prevent underruns, thus stabilising the audio stream [7]. Even in these cases, the delays can be incorporated into the plugin’s latency declaration.

6. PRELIMINARY TESTS

RhizomeBridge underwent preliminary tests designed to isolate and verify specific functions and communication paths. The goal was to observe temporal consistency, alignment between streams, and stability of the system’s synchronous behaviour. Measurements were taken without DAW latency compensation, thereby verifying the system’s behaviour transparently.

Browser-based scenarios were tested using current versions of Chrome and Firefox on both desktop and mobile platforms. Latency was measured by recording signals at transmission and reception points and estimating delay via waveform comparison. Tests were carried out on an Intel-based Mac and on an Apple M4 system, both running macOS Sequoia. These measurements should not be taken as formal benchmarks but as verification of functional behaviour under controlled yet realistic conditions.

6.1 Bidirectional MIDI Loop Test

In this test, bidirectional MIDI flow between the DAW and Node.js was verified. Note messages were initially sent from the JUCE plugin via shared memory, read by a native add-on in Node.js, and processed in real time by reducing their velocity parameter by 50%. The modified messages were then routed back into the DAW through the MIDI input channel, completing a full round-trip cycle.

This test allowed us to evaluate the synchronisation between MIDI messages and the audio stream, as well as the reliability of the semaphore-based synchronisation mechanism. Since processing took place internally in Node.js and without any form of event accumulation, there was no need to implement ring buffer structures.

The measured latency was minimal: the MIDI data returned to the DAW in the audio processing block immediately following transmission, with a latency time of approximately 3 ms, corresponding to a buffer size of 128 samples with a sample rate of 44.1 kHz.

6.2 Bidirectional Audio Test with Asynchronous Processing

In the second test, a complete DAW → Node.js → DAW audio cycle was implemented. The mono audio blocks generated were sent to a Node.js environment and then reinserted into the DAW after being processed. The processing was carried out using the `node-web-audio-api` library, developed

by IRCAM, which reproduces a Web Audio API-compatible environment within Node.js.

In this specific case, the signal was attenuated using a `GainNode` with a linear gain factor of 0.5, serving as a simple test operation to verify the signal path. Since the library operates on minimum blocks of 256 samples, it was necessary to introduce a ring buffer structure on the Node.js side to accumulate at least 512 samples before activating the Web Audio graph, thus ensuring temporal continuity in the output stream. A second ring buffer was also set up within the JUCE plugin, during the return signal reading phase, to compensate for any misalignment between the input stream and the current processing window.

Overall, the latency measured in this configuration was 1024 samples, corresponding to approximately 23 ms at 44.1 kHz. Throughout the test, the system remained stable, glitch-free and consistent in the perceived audio stream.

6.3 Bidirectional Audio Roundtrip via WebRTC and AudioWorklet

A third scenario involved a complete stereo round-trip cycle: DAW → Node.js → Web Audio App → Node.js → DAW, in which the audio signal generated by the DAW was transmitted via WebRTC protocol from Node.js to a local browser, processed within a chain of Web Audio processing nodes, and then returned to the DAW following the reverse path, also via WebRTC. In this configuration, the DAW was set with a buffer size of 128 samples at 44.1 kHz, in line with the native behaviour of `AudioWorkletProcessor`, which operates on blocks of the same size. In the browser, the audio signal was received via WebRTC and processed through a chain of three consecutive `AudioWorkletProcessors`: the first implemented a ring read buffer to stabilise the asynchronous input stream; the second applied a low-pass filter; the third prepared the data for return transmission. From there, the signal was forwarded to the DAW via shared memory. To ensure consistent synchronisation, a ring buffer with similar characteristics to the previous one was used, also on the plugin receiving side.

The total round-trip latency remained within approximately 30 ms, in line with the expected cumulative delay introduced by WebRTC transmission, ring buffering, and audio block alignment along the pipeline.

6.4 Real-Time DAW-to-Browser Transmission in a Performance Context

A final test was carried out during the performance of Void, a composition for Live Electronics and Web App by Lorenzo Ballerini, presented at Tempo Reale (Villa Strozzi, Florence, May 2025, see Figure 4). In this context, RhizomeBridge was used in a unidirectional DAW → Node.js → browser setup to transmit audio and MIDI in real time to a visual web page on a dedicated mobile device connected via Ethernet.

The JUCE plugin sent audio and MIDI to Node.js via shared memory and semaphores; Node.js transmitted the two streams to the browser via WebRTC, using two separate `RTCDataChannel` instances: one for uncompressed audio, the other for control data. Within the WebApp, developed in P5.js, MIDI data was used to trigger visual scenes, while audio was streamed and played back in real time.

To ensure playback stability, it was necessary to introduce a browser-side ring buffer slightly larger than in the previous

test, in order to compensate for micro-variations introduced by the network and the computational load associated with graphics rendering.

The smartphone acted as an isolated audiovisual node within the space, emitting sounds and images independently from the main sound-system. This intentional disconnection highlighted the work's exploration of the theme of isolation through connection and fragmented perception.

The overall latency was about 50 ms, later compensated for within the DAW. For this performance context, the delay remained acceptable and free of jitter.

Figure 4: Live electronics performance of *Void* by Lorenzo Ballerini, Tempo Reale, May 2025. Ph. © The Factory PRD / Archivio di Tempo Reale

6.5 System consistency and stability

In all tests, RhizomeBridge demonstrated strong consistency in the synchronous management of audio and MIDI streams. This was made possible by the shared binary structure of memory segments and the use of a common `frameId` for both domains, which ensured deterministic alignment of audio and MIDI blocks. The `sampleIndex` parameter embedded in each MIDI message also allowed for precise positioning of events within blocks. Extensive testing showed no noticeable event loss or desynchronisation, even under sustained load. The explicit use of POSIX semaphores, combined with buffer-ready flags, prevented race conditions and ensured robust synchronisation. This was verified on multiple instances of the plugin and simultaneous Node.js clients. Overall, the system proved to be stable, predictable, and suitable for real-time interaction in modular environments.

7. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS

RhizomeBridge has some technical limitations that should be considered, alongside specific directions for future development.

The use of shared memory and POSIX semaphores imposes constraints related to compatibility between operating systems, especially on Windows, where implementation requires specific adaptations.

Since the current design adopts a blocking-oriented approach, future iterations will also implement standard techniques to eliminate even the minimal theoretical risk of semaphore-induced blocking. Possible strategies include: semaphore timeouts, where the consumer waits a maximum of 3–5 ms before resetting the state and injecting neutral data; inter-process heartbeat/watchdog signals to detect and recover from producer stalls; automatic fallback to neutral data in case of prolonged waits. These techniques, already established in real-time audio systems, ensure stream continuity, minimise latency impact, and eliminate the possibility of prolonged deadlocks.

The management of SHM segments, which is currently static, could pose scalability issues: as the number of audio channels or MIDI voices increases, the preventive allocation of very large blocks risks becoming inefficient in terms of both memory and flow management, suggesting the future need for a dynamic strategy or distribution across multiple independent buffers.

To accommodate heterogeneous and shared scenarios (local Node.js processing, browser-centred pipelines, or distributed peers over WebRTC), the system should provide automatic latency detection at start-up together with user-configurable offsets. An initial calibration phase can estimate end-to-end delay and jitter, inform ring buffer sizing, and update the plugin's declared latency, reducing manual setup and ensuring consistent behaviour across different hosts and topologies.

As with any plugin hosted in a DAW, overall latency is inherently influenced by the audio buffer size configured at the source. Although RhizomeBridge preserves sample-level timing consistency and accuracy, its actual responsiveness will reflect the real-time configuration of the host system.

In the current implementation, the threads handling inter-process communication via shared memory and semaphores operate at standard priority, particularly on the Node.js side. Tests show that latency and jitter remain extremely low in this configuration, but future versions will consider adopting high-priority, real-time thread scheduling.

8. CONCLUSIONS

The project provides a concrete method for integrating native audio environments (e.g. VST/AU plugins) with the Node.js ecosystem in a bidirectional manner, maintaining temporal precision and consistency in the transmission of audio and control data. Its architecture provides a concrete and adaptable infrastructure that allows developers and artists to design across heterogeneous environments.

The system enables a stable connection between web-based audio and visual processing, communication with IoT devices, shared applications and the native processing pipeline of the DAW. Thanks to the architectural neutrality of the Node.js layer, these bidirectional pathways can be ex-

tended or reconfigured without modifying the system core, allowing for hybrid workflows across native and web-based environments.

In combination with WebRTC and low-latency protocols, it opens up new possibilities for hybrid local/distributed architectures, while preserving fine-grained control over timing and synchronisation.

RhizomeBridge aims to be a tool available to those who design sound and multimedia environments, reactive systems or interactive musical practices; an open and solid structure, capable of communicating with different contexts, where technical requirements intertwine with expressive ones.

9. REFERENCES

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